

ISic0263

I.Sicily inscription 0263

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR127545

1. M (arco) Aemilio M (arci) I (iberto)

2. Antho

3. M (arco) Aemilio M (arci) I (iberto)

4. Claro.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285320

EDR 127545

EDCS 22000886

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7300 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 75

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At A1

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